

CONSUMER VALUE CREATION OF LOCAL TOURISM IN SOCIAL MEDIA

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Abstract: *Consumer value is the basic fundamental of marketing communications. Promotional materials on media have to consider the value of consumer expectations, wishes, experiences, and perceptions. This means product or service has to interact with consumers (need, expectation, experience, and perception). The emergence of new media becomes an alternative for marketers to promote goods or services to their target market. But the emergence of this new media in addition to being an opportunity also becomes a challenge in presenting the best consumer value. The purpose of this research is to find out the ways of creating the value of local tourism on social media. The researcher chooses the official account of Twitter of Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java as an object of research. Two focus of this research is promotional content on the official account of Twitter and consumer value creation. This research is content analysis. The purpose of this research is the identification of value and effort of tourism consumer value creation, especially on social media. The output of this research is patterns of consumer tourism value-creation. Consumer value creation is not applied in visual and textual comprehensively. In addition, based on the content of this account, the local tourist is as the main target market. The values in this account are created for local tourists and not for international tourists.*

Keyword: *consumer, value, tourism, tourism marketing*

Introduction

Value and consumer value is one of the most fundamental concepts in transactional marketing or relational marketing (Boysen Anker, Sparks, Moutinho, & Grönroos, 2015). The Kotlerian conception indicates that implications concerning consumer value are central to our understanding of marketing and, indeed, that the concept of consumer value constitutes the foundation, defining basis, or underlying rationale for the marketing concept in the sense that each party to a transaction gives up one thing in return for something else of greater value (Holbrook, 1998). Customer value can be defined as the excess of the benefits that are subjectively perceived by the customer over the subjectively perceived costs associated with the purchase and use of the product (Szymura-Tyc on Szwajlik, 2016). The benefits the customer reaps are related to the needs he or she intends to satisfy by purchasing and using the product. Individual consumers are mostly looking for benefits associated with satisfying their existential, social, and psychological needs (Szwajlik, 2018). In the market environment, where the concept of value has shifted from a functional benefit to the value of

experience and status (Schmitt on Yuksel & Yanik, 2014). Holbrook and Hirschman (Holbrook, 1998) stated that consumer value resides not in the product purchased, not in the brand chosen, not in the object possessed, but rather in the consumption experience(s) derived therefrom. Previous segmentation studies identified the three categories of consumer needs: are Functional needs (e.g. quality seeker); Social needs (social directed\environmental directed); and Experiential needs (taste, pleasure\gratification) (Humayun, 2009).

This concept of value can be applied to various industrial fields. The previous studies observed consumer value in the food industry (Humayun, 2009; Hassan & Hamdan, 2012) other in banking products (Laukkanen & Lauronen, 2005). They urged understanding how customers perceive value in various service contexts can increase the quality of strategic decision-making, leading to improved customer orientation. So that in the process of creating consumer value, the most important thing is how consumers perceive the products or services, associated with the values expected or believed by consumers. The values discussed above are related to the product or service in the application of the product or service company. Then what about the tourism industry? What values are then offered and how to define and build consumer value in the tourism industry, especially in the digital era (social media)? This is actually a fundamental question in this study.

Social media has its own strengths and ways of displaying and presenting consumer values and perceptions about products and services, especially in tourism. Technological development and the wind of social networks entirely shape the world of tourism, as they do everything. Ten of social networks such as Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Flickr involve many processes, including perceiving, learning, decision-making, and sharing with board convergence without any restrictions of time and space by being backed up by technological tools (Yuksel & Yanik on Prebensen et.al, 2014). Value is centered in the experience of consumers. Tourism experience is not only co-created but increasingly technology-enabled

(Tussaydiah & Fesenmaier, 2007; Tusasaydiah & Zach on Prebensen et.al, 2014). Traveling involves encountering unfamiliar scenes and people, rendering coping and co-creating valuable experiences as situational, and dependent on the skills and knowledge of the tourist (such as socializing, discussing, receiving information, and re-scheduling planned activities) (Prebensen and Foss, 2011 on Prebensen et.al, 2014).

In the context of the global era and consider the technology development, almost entire agency of tourism adopt this technology in the way of they presenting and promoting potency of tourism. One of them is Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java. This official government used Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, Twitter as the social network in socializing and promoting events and tourism potency in West Java. Account of Twitter (@disparbud_jabar) is one of the popular and most attractive and active account. In this account, the Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java presented and informed all activities tourism in West Java by means of picture or video. The purpose of it, absolutely to inform and promote tourism, but the question is “is all kind of material promotion in twitter, represent and relate to tourists value whether are local or international?”, how all of these have values of tourism marketing? These two questions will drive this study to our knowledge about the construction of value in tourism, especially in the digital social network.

Consumer Value in Social Media

Consumer value is an “interactive relativistic preference experience”. This means that for consumer value to emerge a consumer has to interact with a corporate object (product/service) in ways that generate a positive experience in the mind of the consumer and thereby satisfy a personal preference in a given situation (Boysen Anker et al., 2015). Thus, “value” extends beyond the co-creation achieved in customer-service provider interactions, to the value that emerges for customers in the complex mental and material context(s) of their

daily lives (FitzPatrick, Varey, Grönroos, & Davey, 2015). Moreover, “by providing potential value, the firm is a facilitator of value for the customer” (Grönroos and Voima, on FitzPatrick et al., 2015). The customer provides potential value for the firm in the experiential-use processes of the firm. Hence, the firm creates its own value-in-use, in terms of revenue, learning, network connections and so on. The firm’s creation of potential value for the customer, which includes branding (price, “value ‘proposition’” – “suggesting value”, etc.), selling, advertising and promotion (literally “putting forward”), is premised on the anticipation of value-in-use for both the customer and the firm itself. In this way, as expressed by Grönroos in his 2012 model of value co-creation in service, value generation is reciprocal and dialogical (FitzPatrick et al., 2015). In other words, firms offer value propositions and customers accept those value propositions and collaborate in the creation of value (Vargo & Lusch, on Loane & Webster, 2014). Communication between firms and customers today is facilitated by internet connectivity and allows for new forms of collaboration unbounded by geography and on a scale previously unimaginable (Benkler, on Loane & Webster, 2014), especially when social media arouse.

Social media defined as in general social networking sites, which are technologically developed to allow users to create and exchange content. From the perspective of the issue of engagement, in accordance with the Kaplan classification, the most attractive form of Social Media is 'social networks' and 'virtual worlds'. In the context of social capital, in which the capital, similarly to the capital in the economic context, perceives the social relations and network connections between individuals as a resource, to which it is possible to achieve the intended benefits. Social media is a channel that is credited with building the value (Kucharska, 2015)(Marketingu & Wood, 2015).

Method

This study is qualitative research. The selection of this approach is based on the problems and objectives of the research, as well as the object of research related to the content analysis of Twitter account of Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java (@disparbud_jabar) for 1 month (August 2018). The content analysis applied to the image, video, comment, like and retweets of the account. Then, these are categorized into nature and quality of information, finally, these category analyzed by the theoretical framework to see the value, strength and the way of construction tourism value in relation with effective tourism marketing.

Finding and Discussion

Profile of Twitter account of Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java

The official account of Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java registered on Twitter in 2010 by name of Disparbud Jabar (@disparbud_jabar). Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java also registered on Facebook and Instagram. It means that some information on Twitter will be posted on Facebook and Instagram. The followers on Twitter is the biggest number than two others.

Account	Since	Followers	Posts
Twitter	2010	5.082	4.701
Instagram	2017	3.284	590
Facebook	2011	3.234	

Table 1 Social media

It indicates that the Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java strengthening the power of social network (Twitter) as the medium of socializing and promoting tourism. The basic reason is spreading information through social media much faster than conventional media, and it much efficient and effective in this era.

Tweetreach.com recorded for August 2018, information on Twitter account of Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java has reached 476,986 Twitter account.

Picture 1. Twitter Exposure
Source: Tweetreach.com (18 August 2018)

The following picture is home of official Twitter account of Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java.

Picture 2. Official Account of West Java Tourism Office
Source: Twitter.com

On the profile picture, the admin used the official logo of West Java Tourism. This logo used for the branding of tourism and it associated with Indonesian tourism logo. By this means hopefully constructed homogenize branding of Indonesia tourism i.e. “Wonderful Indonesia” or “*Pesona Indonesia*” in Bahasa. Then the content consists of texts, images, and videos. Generally, the content divided into two parts: information about tourism activities in West Java and information about the activities of officials, the Minister, Governor and Head of Tourism Office of West Java. During August 2018 there were 67 tweets consist of 57 tweets are texts and images and 10 tweets are texts and videos. The text has two structures, namely text with headline and body copy, and full body copy. For example text with format headline and body copy:

PEMPROV JABAR KEMBALI GELAR COOPERATIVE FAIR 2018 DI GEDUNG SATE

Wargi jabar kami mengajak kembali wargi jabar ke halaman gedung sate tanggal 10-12 Agustus 2018 dalam Cooperative Fair15 2018 Jabar (Tweet on 9 August 2018).

And other one is example of text with full body copy:

Ikuti kemeriahan Pagelaran seni Helaran di kota bogor. Rangkaian kegiatan ini dalam rangka Hari jadi Bogor (HJB) ke- 536, helaran seni budaya, atraksi seni dan pawai mobil hias bertempat di sepanjang jln sudirman Kota Bogor. (Tweet on 9 August 2018)

The response from followers to information in this account is actually still low. This is indicated by the number of comments, likes, and retweets that are still low, even dominated by the same followers. Video content, the viewer looks much more impressive than the format of text and images.

Responses				
Like	Retweet	Comment	Viewers	Nationality
53	36	1	338	Indonesia

Table 2. Twitter Responses

The content and interpretation of tourism marketing on Twitter

During August 2018, the official Twitter account of Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java posted 67 tweets consist of 57 tweets are texts and images and 10 tweets are texts and videos as displayed below:

NO	CATEGORY OF INFORMATION	STRUCTURE CONTENT		TOTAL
		Picture	Video	
1	Historical Tourism	1		1
2	Art & Cultural Tourism	15	3	18
3	Natural Tourism	5	2	7
4	Sport	14	4	17
5	Public Transportation	1		1
6	Annual Event	13		13
7	Culinary Tourism	1		1
8	Charity	1		1
9	Industrial Tourism	1		1
10	Spiritual Tourism	1		1
11	Official Info	10	1	11
	TOTAL	63	10	72

Table 3. Content of Twitter
Adapted from Twitter.com

There are a number of posts that actually contain different categories of characters, so the number of details is different from the total number of posts (67 Tweet). From the previous data indicate that art and culture, and sports (Asean Games) dominated entirely of the content of the official Twitter account of Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java. Therefore, art & cultural tourism become tourism objects that are encouraged and offered by the Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java to the tourists. Sport dominates with regard to the euphoric moment of the Asean Games held in several regions including the West Java region. The admin of this official account uses this moment as the way to increase public interest. Because this moment is becoming a public interest at that time.

The third rank is occupied by the annual event. This category is actually related to various annual events held by the Government of West Java and by regions in West Java. The

annual event itself can take the form of such as independence day, festival or tourism ambassador election. The fourth rank is the official info. This category information is related to official activities of the Minister, Governor, and Head of Tourism Office. This information indicates that the official account is used not only as a media for promoting West Java tourism but also as a medium for socializing activities or institutional information. So we can conclude from the character of the content of this Twitter account, actually, the tourism agency of West Java does not make this a mere media for tourism promotion. So we can explain this media as a medium for tourism marketing and the other for official information.

Consumer value dimensions of tourism marketing on Twitter

When this account serves as a medium of socialization with effect on marketing, it means that the marketing does not become a core concept in presenting tourism to the tourists especially foreign tourists. This is what happens later in the official Twitter account of Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java. Overall, the content does not fully deliver consumer value. Wish, experience, need, virtual imagery are not fully presented in the media moreover dialogue interactively and persuasive. Actually when followers saw the pictures or videos in the Twitter are constructed co-creation value, whether it is value-in-product, value-in-use, or value-in-service. Consumer perception is conducted by a combination of information elements, whether text, images or videos. All synergies constructed the same message that will support each other in the meaning of a message. Even so, in some posts, pictures and videos have certain values, such as in table 4:

No	Tweet	Value	Content
1	Orchid Forest Cikole, Kembangkan Destinasi Digital di Bandung. Kementerian Pariwisata (Kemenpar) melakukan penandatanganan MoU dengan Orchid Forest Cikole sebagai salah satu Co-Branding Partners di Lembang, Bandung. https://bit.ly/2Bd90h3	Comfort	
2	Siapa yang rindu panganan jadul pada jamannya? Makanan tadi 10ias kalian dapatkan hanya di Pasar Cijaringao yang akan tayang perdana yang berlokasi di Cijaringao, Desa Cimeunyan, Kabupaten Bandung, Jawa Barat. https://bit.ly/2Mz36vq	Taste	
3	Pemkab Cianjur Gelar Ragam Seni Budaya Yang Dikemas Dalam 70 Ribu Detik Cianjur Jago Festival Sabtu, 18 Agustus 2018. Ragam Seni Budaya Nusantara Di 70 Ribu Detik Cianjur Jago Festival 2018. https://bit.ly/2whBuAu	Diversity	
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UPACARA ADAT SEREN TAUN 1951 CAKA SUNDA AKAN BERLANGSUNG TANGGAL 29 AGUSTUS – 3 SEPTEMBER 2018 DI CIGUGUR KUNINGAN. https://bit.ly/2LmG06v • Keunikan Tradisi Ngubek Lauk Di Sungai Cimandiri Sukabumi https://bit.ly/2wdURLU 	Uniqueness	
5	Dengan semangat menyongsong Hari Ulang Tahun Republik Indonesia ke-73 tahun, Jatiwangi Cup yang ke empat kembali digelar di Desa Burujul Wetan, Kecamatan Jatiwangi, Sabtu 11 Agustus 2018. https://bit.ly/2BcL5yv	Strength	

Table 4. Value on Twitter

Conclusion

The content in the official account of Government Tourism and Culture Office of West Java is presented more official information than tourism potency of West Java. So, in one side this account used as medium for socializing official activities, other is promoting tourism of West Java. But in the perspective of consumer value, the content do not cultivate consumer value wheter in the texts and the pictures. Persuasive imagery is not created wheter in the texts or pictures. In the perspective of consumer value, value is the core in production a message to consumer based on their functional, existential, social, psychological needs, experiential needs. The messages of these needs are not presented completely and comprehensively. This official account still more informative than persuasive. In addition, the content of this account represent the local tourist and they as the main target market. Thefore, values in this account are created for local tourists and not for international tourists.

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